

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

SDC4

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	6385/ P31431/ -
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
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CONTENTS OF TEP

Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Validated antibodies & generic knockout cell lines: YCharOS antibody characterization report

Protein constructs & expression methods: Mammalian produced ectodomain; bacterially produced binding partner SDCBP.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and MDK (1).

TREAT-AD Overall Score: 3.75 (rank #930)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Overall Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Overall Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. The Center has also ranked the recency of a target's association with AD in published literature. The Literature Recency Score is on a scale of 0 to 2, with 2 being all papers linking a target and AD have been published in the most recent 5 year period. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v33.

The TREAT-AD Overall score for this target is 3.75 out of 5 (rank #930). The individual score components include 1.76 of 3 for genetics, and 2 out of 2 for genomics. The literature recency score is 0.89 out of 2. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of SDC4, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. The biological domain characterization of the source module (Module 42) indicates that the proteins in this module are enriched for terms annotated to the Structural Stabilization, Synapse, Lipid Metabolism, and APP Metabolism domains. The most significantly enriched terms from this module are "collagen-containing extracellular matrix", "basement membrane", and "endoplasmic reticulum lumen". SDC4 is annotated to GO terms primarily from the Structural Stabilization, Endolysosome, and Lipid Metabolism biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Allen Brain Institute. The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins, points indicating the expression of the target in specific subtypes within each broad class including a label for the highest expressing cell type for each broad class. These data indicate that SDC4 is expressed in astrocytes in healthy adult brains.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Syndecan-4 (SDC4) is a member of a family of syndecan transmembrane receptors, which interact with a variety of extracellular targets. Syndecan signalling leads to endocytosis, endosomal sorting, and exosome export of bound ligands, a process which is dependent on the binding of syndecan-binding protein (SDCBP) to the intracellular tails of syndecans. Cellular trafficking of A β is dependent on syndecan/SDCBP activity (2). SDC4 was found within a TMT proteomics network module (Module 42) that contains mostly novel but also well-known AD targets, whose levels are elevated in AD patient brains (1). Inhibition of SDC4 signalling is predicted to reduce the A β burden in AD patient brains (3).

The aim of this TEP is to generate reagents useful for investigating the role of SDC4 in Alzheimer's disease, such as a list of validated antibodies, generic knockout/knockdown cell lines and purified protein. Two therapeutic strategies for inhibition of SDC4 will be investigated in this TEP: 1. inhibition of SDC4 activity with an antibody and 2. inhibition of interaction of SDC4 C-terminal tail with SDCBP with small molecules.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

SDC4 (Syndecan-4) is a transmembrane proteoglycan involved in numerous signalling events, including cell proliferation, migration, and endocytosis (4). It is a member of a class of four syndecans that have quite divergent domains that are external to the cell (or ectodomains) but all contain highly conserved transmembrane and cytoplasmic regions. Multiple heparin sulfate chains are linked to the ectodomains of syndecans, allowing them to interact with a wide variety of ligands, including growth factors and cytokines. Syndecans can also undergo regulated proteolytic cleavage, called shedding. Release of syndecan ectodomains may downregulate signalling by competing with extracellular ligands.

Analysis of post-mortem brain tissue identified SDC4 as highly enriched in AD patients (1). Syndecans can promote the seeding and spreading of tau and α -synuclein, a hallmark of AD (5). One of the functions of syndecans is to mediate endocytosis through their clustering of cargo in lipid rafts prior to their internalization. This process depends on the binding of the cytoplasmic tail of syndecan to ERM (ezrin, radixin and moesin) proteins, which in turn is associated with the actin cytoskeleton. Recycling of syndecans and their cargo to the plasma membrane can occur through the interaction of the extreme C-terminal region of the cytoplasmic tail with a variety of PDZ domain-containing proteins, including syntenin (SDCBP). Alternatively, SDCBP can reroute the trafficking of syndecans and their cargo towards intraluminal vesicles, which are released from the cell as exosomes, a process that requires the endosomal sorting complex ESCRT (3). SDCBP is required for endosomal trafficking and exosome secretion of A β through the ESCRT pathway (2). Exosomes carrying amyloid may contribute to plaque deposition and neurotoxicity in AD. Either inhibition of SDC4 interaction with SDCBP, or inhibition of SDC4 signalling through the ectodomain (using an antibody or small molecule) is expected to reduce A β deposition and neurotoxicity.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

YCharOS (<https://ycharos.com/>) is an open science organisation which has industrialised a knockout based antibody characterization platform formalised at the Montreal Neurological Institute (6) with the mission to characterize antibodies against the human proteome. YCharOS has created an open scientific ecosystem in which antibody manufacturers and knockout cell line suppliers contribute reagents to support the YCharOS' goal.

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for SDC4. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. YCharOS has identified MCF7 as a cell line with adequate expression of SDC4, and developed an MCF7 knockout line using siRNA technology. These two lines (WT and KO) were used to characterise ten commercially available antibodies. All except one antibodies tested were polyclonal. The full antibody characterisation report is available on Zenodo (please follow the link below):

[SDC4 antibody characterization report](#)

Proteins Purified

- 1. SDC4A-c001:** Ectodomain of Human SDC4 (E19-E145). Contains a C-terminal 6His and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.
- 2. SDCBPA-c010:** Tandem PDZ domains of human SDCBP (A106-V298). Protein produced in bacteria.

CONCLUSION

SDC4 is associated with AD pathology. This TEP focuses on the generation of tools to facilitate the investigation of the role of SDC4 in AD, and starting points for developing antibody or small molecule inhibitors.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

- 1. SDC4A-c001:** Human SDC4 ectodomain, E19-E145. Contains an N-terminal secretion signal, a C-terminal His6 and AviTag (allowing in vitro biotinylation, if needed). Protein produced in Expi293F cells.

Construct ID	SDC4A-c001
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Parental vector	pHL-Avitag3
Tag	C-terminal 6His, C-terminal Avitag
Protein mass (with tag)	20552.7 Da (with signal peptide), 17787.1 Da (without signal peptide)
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	6990 (with or without signal peptide)
Protein sequence (with tag)	MGILPSPGMPALLSLVSLLSVLLMGCVAETGESIRETEVIDPQDLLEGRYFSGALPD DEDVVGPGQESDDFELSGSGDLDDLEDSMIGPEVVHPLVPLDNHUPERAGSGSQV PTEPKKLEENEVIPKRISPVEESEDVSNKVSMSSTVQGSNIFERTEGTGGSGGSGLN DIFEAQKIEWHEGRTKHHHHHH

Purified Protein	
SEC: SDC4A-c001 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: SDC4A-c001 (with tag; without signal peptide)	
Observed Mass:	17787 Da
Protein yield:	3.8 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>Mammalian:</i> Expi293F cells (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
Expression medium	FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

Plasmid purification	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain MACH1. Plate on LB-agar plates containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml). Inoculate 5 ml LB broth containing ampicillin (100 µg/ml) with a single colony and grow 6h at 37°C with shaking. Inoculate 800 ml LB broth containing the same antibiotic with 2 ml of starter culture and grow overnight at 37°C with shaking. Split culture into 4 and perform MaxiPrep (Qiagen) with 4 columns according to manufacturer's instructions. Add 0.7 volumes of isopropanol to precipitate the plasmid. Spin (17000g, 30 min, 4°C) and wash pellet with 70% ethanol. Resuspend plasmid with sterile TE buffer under sterile conditions. Yield is typically 2 mg of plasmid.
Transfection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Split Expi293F cells to 1x10⁶ cells/ml in 200 ml FreeStyle 293 Expression Medium. Incubate for 24 h until cells are approximately 2x10⁶ cells/ml (37°C, 150 rpm, 8% CO₂, 75% rh). 2. Add plasmid to 4mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM to 50 µg/ml. 3. Add linear PEI (1 mg/ml sterile stock) to another 4 mL of pre-warmed Opti-MEM to 150 µg/ml. 4. Add the mixture from Step 3 to the one in Step 2 and incubate at room temperature for 30 min. 5. Add the plasmid/PEI mixture slowly to the cells (to give final concentrations of 1 µg/ml plasmid and 3 µg/ml PEI). 6. Add sodium butyrate (1 M sterile stock) to 10 mM concentration. 7. Incubate cells at 30°C (8%CO₂/75% rh) with shaking at 150 rpm. 8. Harvest cell culture supernatant at 4 days post transfection (900g, 20 min, 4°C). 9. Filter supernatant through 0.2 µm filter.
IMAC and SEC purification buffers and reagents	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ni IMAC W10 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 300 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 2. Ni IMAC W25 buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 300 mM NaCl, 25 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol 3. Ni IMAC elution buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 300 mM NaCl, 250 mM imidazole, 2% glycerol 4. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Ni IMAC W10 buffer. 5. DPBS: TC-grade (ThermoFisher)
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add imidazole to filtered supernatant to 10 mM final concentration. 2. Add a total of 1 ml equilibrated Ni-sepharose beads to the cell supernatant, split into 50-ml falcon tubes. Mix by rotation overnight in at 4°C. 3. Spin beads/supernatant slurry (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant supernatant and wash beads with 50 ml W10 buffer. Transfer beads to transfer a gravity column 4°C. 4. Wash column with 40 ml W25.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Elute protein with 1x 7.5 ml elution buffer, followed by 1x5 ml elution buffer. Analyse the elution fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. Pool elution fractions containing protein.
Purification step 2: SEC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Concentrate pooled IMAC elution fractions to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. Perform SEC on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column, equilibrated in DPBS, at 1 ml/min. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 1-5 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

2. SDCBPA-c010: Tandem PDZ domains of human SDCBP (A106-V298). Protein produced in bacteria.

Construct ID	SDCBPA-c010
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal 6His-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	23867.6 Da
Protein mass (with tag removed)	21401.9 Da
Extinction Coefficient (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	6990
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAEIKQGIREVILCKDQDGKIGLRLKSIDNGIFVQLVQ ANSPASLVGLRFGDQVLQINGENCAGWSSDKAHKVLKQAFGEKITMTIRDRPFERTITM HKDSTGHVGFIFKNGKITSIVKSSAARNLLTEHNICEINGQNVIGLKDSQIADILSTSGT VVTITIMPAFIFEHIKRMAPSIMKSLMDHTIPEV
Protein sequence (after tag removal)	SMAEIKQGIREVILCKDQDGKIGLRLKSIDNGIFVQLVQANSPASLVGLRFGDQVLQINGE NCAGWSSDKAHKVLKQAFGEKITMTIRDRPFERTITM HKDSTGHVGFIFKNGKITSIVKD SSAARNLLTEHNICEINGQNVIGLKDSQIADILSTSGTVVTITIMPAFIFEHIKRMAPSIM KSLMDHTIPEV

Purified Protein

SEC: SDCBPA-c010 (tag removed)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: SDCBPA-c010 (tag removed)	
Observed Mass:	21402 Da
Protein yield:	20 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP

	5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.6 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 100 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 20 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 10 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight. 2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.6 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 10 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The cleaved protein is normally recovered in the flowthrough, Lysis, or W30 fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease are present in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S75 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein with desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

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